

K-Medoids and Fuzzy K-Medoids Methods with Euclidean Distance and Dynamic Time Warping in Time Series Data Open Unemployment Rate

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 08 June 2026	Open Unemployment Rate (OUR) data is a time series dataset that shows changes over time and often has similar patterns across regions. This study aims to cluster Indonesian provinces based on OUR change patterns using a whole-time-series clustering approach. Each province is treated as a single complete time series, and clustering is performed based on pattern similarities rather than only comparing values at specific time points. Two clustering methods are used: K-Medoids and Fuzzy K-Medoids. These methods are with two distance measures, Euclidean distance and Dynamic Time Warping (DTW), resulting in four clustering methods. DTW is applied to capture flexible pattern similarities in time series data, while Euclidean distance measures direct value differences. The quality of clustering results is evaluated using the silhouette coefficient. The results show that the Fuzzy K-Medoids – DTW combination with 2 clusters produces the highest silhouette score = 0.627, indicating the best clustering structure among all tested methods. These findings suggest that combining fuzzy clustering with DTW distance is more suitable for OUR data, which tend to have smooth changes and similar patterns across provinces.
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I. INTRODUCTION

The progress and welfare of a country are measured by the growth and quality of economic development in it. Based on the report World Economic Outlook from the International Monetary Fund as of April 2024, placing the unemployment rate in Indonesia as the highest in ASEAN, at 5.2%, and remaining at the level of 5% in 2025 [1]. This figure places Indonesia as one of the countries with the highest unemployment rate in ASEAN. Open Unemployment Rate (TPT) is the percentage of the number of unemployed to the total labor force, which, if the TPT decreases, shows positive economic growth conditions [2].

In reality, the unemployment gap between provinces in Indonesia is also still visible. In 2024, TPT, based on a report from the Sakernas Booklet [3], is at its highest in provinces such as Banten, Riau, and West Java, while the provinces of Mountainous Papua, Bali, and Central Papua are in the lowest TPT positions. This is also supported by the results of TPT clustering research in the range of 2020 to 2024 conducted by Karim et al. [4] that the highest TPT consists of 4 provinces, namely Riau District, DKI Jakarta, West Java, and Banten.

Meanwhile, in 2025, the composition of the provinces with the highest and lowest TPT will shift slightly. The provinces with the highest TPT are occupied by the provinces of Papua, Riau Islands, and West Java, while the provinces with the lowest TPT are the provinces of Bali, Mountainous Papua, and Central Sulawesi. This condition shows that the problem of TPT in Indonesia is not just a number, but also how the burden of unemployment is spread unevenly between provinces.

Research on the grouping of time series data has been carried out using various methods and distance metrics. One of the previous studies conducted by Aqsari et al. [5] used the K-Means with distance metrics, Dynamic Time Warping to classify the stock price of the financial sector based on its fluctuations in a one-year period. The results of the study showed that the use of the distance metric Dynamic Time Warping generates a value silhouette higher than the distance metric Euclidean. The next research was carried out because the time series data have high-dimensional characteristics, contain time shifts, and show similarities in patterns that are not aligned, making it difficult to group using clustering methods and distance metrics in general. This research was

conducted by Izakian et al. [6] using eight time series datasets from the UCR repository. The results showed that the three DTW-based methods produced better grouping quality compared to Fuzzy C-Means with Euclidean distance (FCM-EU), both in terms of accuracy and representation of the shape of the cluster center. Research conducted by Holder et al. [7] shows that Dynamic Time Warping is not always superior to Euclidean distance. In their big experiment, DTW actually performed worse than Euclidean distance on the clustering of time series with K-Means, and is not significantly better when combined with K-Medoids.

In this study, two types of distance measurements, namely Euclidean and Dynamic Time Warping, were used to see how the two distance methods compare when applied to time series data. In addition, two different types of clustering methods were also used, namely soft clustering (Fuzzy K-Medoids) and hard clustering (K-Medoids), to see the combination between the two distance methods when applied to each clustering method. To see the quality of clusters resulting from the combination of both distance and clustering methods, the Silhouette Index metric is used, which is expected to produce accurate provincial mapping, so that later it can be useful as the basis for more targeted employment policies for the central and regional governments in understanding the characteristics of regional groups with similar patterns of unemployment movements.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Cluster analysis is a statistical technique used to group objects into several groups (cluster) with the aim that objects in one group have similar characteristics, while objects in different groups have differences [8]. In cluster analysis, the concept of distance is the basis for measuring the degree of similarity or dissimilarity between two objects or two time series. The smaller the distance between two objects, the greater the degree of similarity, and vice versa [9].

Euclidean distance is a metric that is often used to measure how far apart two time series are in a grouping. This distance works directly comparing the corresponding data points at any time in time.

The *j* provincial data in this study is defined as a time series vector that represents the value of the Open Unemployment Rate (TPT) from the period 2015 to 2025. The data object is expressed as:

$$a_j = (a_{j1}, a_{j2}, \dots, a_{jT}) \tag{1}$$

where a_{j1} is the value of the Open Unemployment Rate (TPT) in the province *j* for the time period to-*t*, with $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ and $n = 34$, and $t \in \{1, 2, \dots, T\}$ for $T = 22$. The calculation of the distance between two provinces is carried out by comparing a_j and a_h , which *h* is the index of the comparative provinces.

The distance between the two time series is calculated using the formula:

$$d_{(a_j, a_h)} = \sqrt{\sum_{t=1}^T (a_{jt} - a_{ht})^2} \tag{2}$$

where,

- j, h* : Provincial Index
- t* : Time Period Index
- $d_{(a_j, a_h)}$: Euclidean distance between the provinces to-*j* and provinces to-*h*
- a_{jt} : the value of the time series data of the province to-*j* in the time period to-*t*
- a_{ht} : the value of time series data of the province to-*h* in the time period to-*t*
- n* : the number of provinces, in this study $n = 34$
- T* : the maximum limit of the observation period, i.e. $T = 22$

If there are many variables, then the calculation results can be in the form of a distance matrix (d_{euclid} containing $d_{(a_j, a_h)}$) with a size ($n \times n$), where *n* is the number of provinces of the observed data.

$$d_{euclid} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & d_{a_1, a_2} & d_{a_1, a_3} & \dots & d_{a_1, a_n} \\ d_{a_2, a_1} & 0 & d_{a_2, a_3} & \dots & d_{a_2, a_n} \\ d_{a_3, a_1} & d_{a_3, a_2} & 0 & \dots & d_{a_3, a_n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ d_{a_n, a_1} & d_{a_n, a_2} & d_{a_n, a_3} & \dots & 0 \end{bmatrix} \tag{3}$$

In contrast to distance Euclidean that calculates the resemblance perpendicular (one to one) along the time axis, which means points a_{11} can only be compared to or between points with the same index, according to Petitjean et al. [10] Dynamic Time Warping able to perform optimal alignment (optimal alignment) by allowing a single point of the time series province to *j* (a_j) to match (aligned) with multiple points from the time series Province to *h* (a_h), and vice versa. Suppose there are two provincial series, namely the reference time series denoted as $a_j = (a_{j1}, a_{j2}, \dots, a_{jT})$ and the comparative time series denoted as $a_h = (a_{h1}, a_{h2}, \dots, a_{hT})$, the algorithm constructs a $T \times T$ -sized cost matrix. Recursive formulas Dynamic Time Warping defined as follows:

$$D(a_j, a_h)|_t = \delta(a_{jt}, a_{ht}) + \min \begin{cases} D(a_{j,t-1}, a_{ht}) & \text{(Upward step)} \\ D(a_{jt}, a_{h,t-1}) & \text{(Downward step)} \\ D(a_{j,t-1}, a_{h,t-1}) & \text{(Diagonal step)} \end{cases} \tag{4}$$

where $j, h = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$ and $t = 1, 2, 3, \dots, T$

The total Dynamic Time Warping distance between two provincial time series a_j and a_h is the cumulative cost value stored in the lower right corner cell of the matrix i.e. $D_{T,T}$ or $D_{22,22}$. This value is then entered into the Dynamic Time Warping Distance (d_{DTW}) which is distance matrix 34×34 sized.

Distance matrix Euclidean and Dynamic Time Warping obtained then used as the basis for grouping using K-Medoids and Fuzzy K-Medoids. K-Medoids is a grouping method that falls under the category *hard clustering* Center-based (centroid based). *hard clustering* is a method of data grouping where each point is assigned to one and only one cluster [11].

K-Medoids algorithm in detail according to Kaufman and Rousseeuw [12] consists of two phases, namely the *BUILD* and phase *SWAP*. The first medoid selection can be done by looking for the object that has the smallest total distance from all other objects defined as:

$$w_j = \sum_{h=1}^n d_{(a_j, a_h)} \quad (5)$$

n : the number of provinces (in this study $n = 34$)
 j : Index of provinces that are being evaluated as Medoid candidates
 h : Index of all provinces that are a comparison with the provinces to- j
 w_j : Total Distance to j
 $d_{(a_j, a_h)}$: Distance between the province j and the province h
 Furthermore, for the selection of the next medoid to the second medoid is used in the BUILD phase as follows:

1. Consider an object i that has not been selected as medoid 1 in the previous process, which object i will later be a candidate to become the next medoid.
2. Consider the unselected objects (all objects including non-medoid) and calculate

$$\Delta_{j,i} = D_j - d_{(a_j, a_i)} \quad (6)$$

$$D_j = d_{(a_j, m_1)} \quad (7)$$

j : index of all provinces
 i : Index of Medoid candidates other than medoid 1
 $\Delta_{j,i}$: Provincial Advantage if Taking Province to Medoid ji new
 D_j : the distance between the object against the first medoid j
 $d_{(a_j, a_i)}$: the distance of the object to the object that is the candidate for the new medoid ji taken from the *Euclidean distance* matrix or DTW.

3. Calculate the contribution value C_{ji} , if the resulting difference is positive or there is a decrease in distance, then the object j will contribute to the decision to choose the object i as the medoid, and if there is no decrease in distance, then the contribution is considered zero.

$$d_{(a_j, a_h)} = \sqrt{\sum_{t=1}^T (a_{jt} - a_{ht})^2}$$

$$C_{ji} = \max(D_j - d_{(a_j, a_i)}, 0) \quad (8)$$

C_{ji} : the contribution of the object if selected as a medoid ji

4. Calculate the total contribution of each object- j obtained by selecting object to- i as a medoid.

$$G_i = \sum_{j=1}^n C_{ji} \quad (9)$$

G_i : Total Gain Candidate Medoid i

5. Select an object i that has not been selected as a medoid with the following criteria:

$$m_{baru} = \max_m G_i \quad (10)$$

After getting the object, then the object is chosen as the second medoid.

6. Calculate the total initial cost
 Mathematically written as:

$$\text{Total Cost} = \sum_{j=1, m \in M}^n \min d_{(a_j, m)} \quad (11)$$

a_j : object to- j in the dataset
 n : the total number of objects in the data
 \mathbf{M} : a set that contains a selected set of medoids
 m : the index of each medoid in the set \mathbf{M}
 $d_{(a_j, m)}$: Distance between the object j and the medoid

Furthermore, for the selection of the best medoids, the *SWAP phase* is used with the aim of improving the selection of medoids that have been obtained in the *BUILD* phase by testing whether there is a medoid that can be replaced with another object so that later it will produce a smaller total distance. The *SWAP* phase is described as follows:

1. Identification of medoid (\mathbf{M}) and non-medoid (\mathbf{O}) objects.
2. Test all medoid and non-medoid pairs for each pair (m, o) with m element \mathbf{M} and o element \mathbf{O} , perform an exchange experiment.

3. Calculate the change in distance for each object, determining whether its distance to the medoid will be smaller or larger if m is replaced by o.
4. Calculate the total deviation (S)

$$S = \text{total cost baru} - \text{total cost lama} \quad (12)$$

5. Choose the best swap and take the pair (m, o) with the S most negative (biggest cost reduction)
6. Do a SWAP if there is a fix, If S is best < 0 then replace m with o as the new medoid.
7. Repeat until there are no negative S, If all S ≥ 0, the iteration process stops until the swap is stable.

Once the SWAP phase ends, and there are no more medoid exchanges that can lower the total cost, the *K-Medoids algorithm* moves on to the cluster determination phase. In this phase, each data object (data j) is allocated to a cluster whose respective medoids indicate a minimum distance to the object.

As the need for more complex data processing grew, the *fuzzy clustering* as a solution. In contrast to *hard clustering* which gives membership 0 or 1, *fuzzy clustering* Included in the category *soft clustering* Where each object is given a degree of membership to each cluster with a value between 0 to 1, so that one object can be "related" to more than one cluster at the same time [11]. Suppose $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$ is n group of objects, and with $M = \{m_1, m_2, \dots, m_k\}$ where k is the number of clusters where $k = 2, 3, 4, 5$. Algorithm *Fuzzy K-Medoids* according to Krishnapuram et al. [13] which are as follows:

1. The medoid is obtained using the *BUILD phase* as much as the initial medoid of the dataset k so that it is obtained $M = \{m_1, m_2, \dots, m_k\}$, where k is the number of predetermined clusters ($k = 2:5$), with the maximum number of iterations $max_iter = 50$.
2. Calculate *fuzzy membership degrees*

$$\mu_{ka_j}^{(r)} = \frac{\left(\frac{1}{d_{(a_j, m_k)}}\right)^{\frac{1}{p-1}}}{\sum_{k=1}^5 \left(\frac{1}{d_{(a_j, m_k)}}\right)^{\frac{1}{p-1}}}$$

$\mu_{ka_j}^{(r)}$: the degree of provincial membership to a_j to the k cluster in the r iteration.

$d_{(a_j, m_k)}$: distance of the provincial object to a_j to the medoid k cluster

m_k : medoid cluster to $-k$

j : Provincial Index

k : Index of number of clusters

p : parameter fuzziness ($p > 1$)

r : Iteration Index

The formula for the degree of membership above is $d_{(a_j, m_k)} \neq 0$, if $d_{(a_j, m_k)} = 0$ then the degree of membership in the object j is completely in the

medoid m_k so that, $\mu_{ka_j}^{(r)} = 1$ and the degree of membership in other medoids is value 0. Membership degree meets:

$$\sum_{k=1}^5 \mu_{ka_j}^{(r)} = 1, \quad j = 1, \dots, n.$$

3. Define a dominant cluster

Each data a_j can be allocated to the cluster k with the largest degree of membership:

$$\text{cluster}(a_j) = \arg \max_k \mu_{ka_j}^{(r)}$$

4. Update the medoid for each cluster, the new medoid $m_k^{(r+1)}$ is obtained by:

$$m_k^{(r+1)} = \arg \min_{i \in X} \sum_{j=1}^n (\mu_{ka_j}^{(r)})^p d_{(a_j, i)}, \quad k = 2, 3, 4, 5$$

$m_k^{(r+1)}$: New medoid for the k cluster in the next iteration, namely notated (r + 1) which is calculated from the membership in iteration now (r).

n : Total of data.

$(\mu_{ka_j}^{(r)})^p$: The degree of fuzzy membership of the a_j object in the k cluster is raised by the fuzziness parameter (p).

$d_{(a_j, i)}$: The distance between the a_j object and the candidate medoid i.

5. Recalculate fuzzy membership degrees.
6. Allocation of objects to clusters, just like step 3, each object can be reallocated to the cluster by selecting the largest degree of membership $\mu_{ka_j}^{(r+1)}$.

7. Calculate objective functions and convergence tests on the first iteration r + 1

$$J_{(r)} = \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^5 (\mu_{ka_j}^{(r)})^p d_{(a_j, m_k)}$$

The iteration will be stopped if any of the following conditions are met:

- The medoid as a result of the medoid update is the same as the medoid in the previous iteration (converged). Mathematically $m^{(t+1)} = m^{(t)}$
 - The number of iterations has reached max_iter
8. Repeat steps 4 through 7 until they converge.

The quality of the results of the cluster method combination was evaluated using *silhouette coefficients* with formula [12]:

$$s(j) = \frac{b(j) - q(j)}{\max\{q(j), b(j)\}}$$

III. METHODOLOGY

The type of data used for this study is quantitative time series data on the Open Unemployment Rate from 34 provinces in Indonesia for the period 2015 to 2025. Open Unemployment Rate data is available for two periods each year: February and August, so each province has 22 data points to observe. The study consists of only one primary variable, the Open Unemployment Rate (TPT) [14]. Data were obtained from the Central Statistics Agency (BPS) through a website publication accessible on the official BPS website, www.bps.go.id. BPS published data is available in percentage units (%). Before further analysis, the data is converted to a decimal scale to simplify calculations.

This study uses Whole Time Series Clustering, where each province is treated as a complete series without any period cuts. Similarities between provinces are determined based on change patterns using a Shaped-Based approach, not simply on similar values at specific times. Therefore, the steps in grouping time series data based on these categories consist of three stages: input, combined with clustering methods and distance measures, to produce output in the form of provincial groupings [9].

The research stages include:

1. Data collection and organization
2. Data preprocessing
3. Calculation of inter-provincial distances using Euclidean distance metrics and Dynamic Time Warping
4. Initialization of initial medoids using the BUILD phase.
5. Clustering process using K-Medoids and Fuzzy K-Medoids
6. Cluster evaluation and interpretation

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

From the results of the distance calculation using two measurement metrics, the following results were compared:

Table 1. Distance Comparison *Euclidean* and *Dynamic Time Warping*

Distance Method	Nearby Provinces	Distance Value	Farthest Province	Distance Value
<i>Euclidean</i>	NTT - Central Sulawesi	0,0153	Banten - Bali	0,27205
<i>Dynamic Time Warping</i>	NTT - Central Sulawesi	0,0436	Banten - Bali	1,2398

Based on the comparison in the table above, it can be seen that the Euclidean distance method and *Dynamic Time Warping* produce similar proximity patterns, but still have

significant differences. In the nearest provincial pair, the *Euclidean* distance metric has a smaller value than *Dynamic Time Warping*. The difference in distance values between the two distance metrics is due to the calculation mechanism. *Euclidean* distance compares two time series point-by-point at the same time, resulting in one direct distance value. In contrast, *Dynamic Time Warping* calculates distances through a time alignment process by constructing a cumulative cost matrix and selecting a minimum path, so that the final distance is obtained from the last element of the *Dynamic Time Warping matrix*. *Dynamic Time Warping* provides a slightly greater value because it takes into account the possibility of time shifts in data movement patterns. *Dynamic Time Warping* is more sensitive because it looks at the shape of the pattern as a whole, not just the values at the same time.

After calculating the distance matrix with the two distance metrics, a clustering process was carried out with the initialization of the medoid treated the same between the four combinations of methods, namely through the BUILD phase. The results of the comparative evaluation of the combination of clustering and distance methods were obtained as follows:

Table 2. Evaluation of Comparative Methods

Method	Distance	k	Early Medoid	Silhouette Score
<i>K-Medoids</i>	<i>Euclidean</i>	2	South Sumatra, North Sulawesi	0,529
		3	South Sumatra, North Sulawesi, Bengkulu	0,347
		4	South Sumatra, North Sulawesi, Bengkulu, West Java	0,342
		5	South Sumatra, North Sulawesi, Bengkulu, West Java, North Sumatra	0,307
		2	North Maluku, Aceh	0,618
<i>Dynamic Time Warping</i>		3	North Maluku, Aceh, East Nusa Tenggara	0,459
		4	North Maluku, Aceh, East Nusa Tenggara, West Java	0,413
		5	North Maluku, Aceh, East Nusa Tenggara, West Java, Bali	0,417
	<i>Euclidean</i>	2	South Sumatra, North Sulawesi	0,534

Fuzzy K-Medoids		3	South Sumatra, North Sulawesi, Bengkulu	0,347
		4	South Sumatra, North Sulawesi, Bengkulu, West Java	0,342
		5	South Sumatra, North Sulawesi, Bengkulu, West Java, North Sumatra	0,307
	Dynamic Time Warping	2	North Maluku, Aceh	0,627
		3	North Maluku, Aceh, East Nusa Tenggara	0,459
		4	North Maluku, Aceh, East Nusa Tenggara, West Java	0,413
		5	North Maluku, Aceh, East Nusa Tenggara, West Java, Bali	0,417

	Southeast Sulawesi, Gorontalo, West Sulawesi, North Maluku, Papua.
2	Aceh, North Sumatra, West Sumatra, Riau Province, DKI Jakarta, West Java, Banten, East Kalimantan, North Sulawesi, Maluku, West Papua.

The two clusters can be defined respectively, namely, cluster 1 describes provinces that have lower TPT. Meanwhile, cluster 2 has a higher unemployment rate and is more volatile than cluster 1.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the analysis of the two distance metrics, it was found that the distance value produced by *Dynamic Time Warping* is greater because it calculates the cumulative cost along the path of time alignment, whereas *Euclidean* only compares points at the same time without an alignment mechanism. The results of the evaluation of the clustering and distance methods showed that the best method in this study for *the time data of* the Open Unemployment Rate was *Fuzzy K-Medoids* with *Dynamic Time Warping* distance which produced *the highest silhouette score* value close to 1 as large as the value based on **0,627** *the silhouette score* criteria table is in a range 0,51 – 0,70 that shows a good cluster structure criterion with the number of clusters, the most optimal is $k = 2$. The characteristics of the resulting clusters are that the first cluster is dominated by provinces with low TPT, while the second cluster contains areas with high and fluctuating TPT.

REFERENCES

1. International Monetary Fund, 2024. World Economic Outlook Database (No. 2015–2025). International Monetary Fund, Washington, D.C.
2. Booklet Sakernas, 2025. Badan Pusat Statistik.
3. Booklet Sakernas, 1st ed, 2024. . Badan Pusat Statistik.
4. Karim, A., Esabella, S., Kusmanto, Suryadi, S., Mardinata, E., 2024. Clusterisasi Tingkat Pengangguran Terbuka Menurut Provinsi di Indonesia Menggunakan Algoritma K-Medoids. Build. Inform. Technol. Sci. BITS 6, 1341–1351. <https://doi.org/10.47065/bits.v6i3.6198>
5. Aqsari, H.W., Prastyo, D.D., Rahayu, S.P., 2022. Clustering Stock Prices of Financial Sector Using K-Means Clustering With Dynamic Time Warping, in: The 6th International Conference on Information Technology, Information Systems and Electrical Engineering (ICITISEE). IEEE, Surabaya, Indonesia, pp. 503–507.

Based on Table 2, the results of the evaluation show that the highest silhouette values are consistently obtained in the number of clusters for all combinations of the distance method and the clustering method. However, overall, *the Fuzzy K-Medoids* method provides a higher silhouette value than the K-Medoids. The combination of the Fuzzy K-Medoids method with the Dynamic Time Warping distance metric yields a higher value than the other combination methods, which is 0.627. This shows that the combination of the grouping method with the distance metric is able to capture the similarity of the TPT time series pattern between provinces better and more flexibly, especially when there are time shifts or variations in patterns that are not simultaneous.

The results of the clustering showed that each province occupying the cluster was given in the following table:

Table 3. Clustered Provinces

Cluster	Province
1	Riau, Jambi, South Sumatra, Bengkulu, Lampung, Bangka Belitung District, Central Java, DI Yogyakarta, East Java, Bali, West Nusa Tenggara, East Nusa Tenggara, West Kalimantan, Central Kalimantan, South Kalimantan, North Kalimantan, Central Sulawesi, South Sulawesi,

<https://doi.org/10.1109/ICITISEE57756.2022.10057714>

6. Izakian, H., Pedrycz, W., Jamal, I., 2015. Fuzzy clustering of time series data using dynamic time warping distance. *Eng. Appl. Artif. Intell.* 39, 235–244.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engappai.2014.12.015>
7. Holder, C., Middlehurst, M., Bagnall, A., 2023. A Review and Evaluation of Elastic Distance Functions for Time Series Clustering. *Knowl. Inf. Syst.* 66, 1–39. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10115-023-01952-0>
8. Kaufman, L., Rousseeuw, P.J., 1990. *Finding Groups in Data: An Introduction to Cluster Analysis*, Wiley Series in Probability and Mathematical Statistics. Wiley, New York.
9. Aghabozorgi, S., Shirkhorshidi, A.S., Wah, T.Y., 2015. Time-series clustering – A decade review. *Inf. Syst.* 53, 16–38.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.is.2015.04.007>
10. Petitjean, F., Ketterlin, A., Gancarski, P., 2011. A global averaging method for dynamic time warping, with applications to clustering. *Pattern Recognit.* 44.
11. Li, H., Wang, J., 2024. From Soft Clustering to Hard Clustering: A Collaborative Annealing Fuzzy c-Means Algorithm. *IEEE Trans. Fuzzy Syst.* 32, 1181–1194.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/TFUZZ.2023.3319663>
12. Kaufman, L., Rousseeuw, P.J., 1990. *Finding Groups in Data: An Introduction to Cluster Analysis*, Wiley Series in Probability and Mathematical Statistics. Wiley, New York.
13. Krishnapuram, R., Joshi, A., Nasraoui, O., Yi, L., 2001. Low-complexity fuzzy relational clustering algorithms for Web mining. *IEEE Trans. Fuzzy Syst.* 9, 595–607. <https://doi.org/10.1109/91.940964>
14. Badan Pusat Statistik, 2025. *Tingkat Pengangguran Terbuka Menurut Provinsi (Persen)*. Badan Pusat Statistik, Jakarta.